

UNDERDOGS: -FROM ADELAIDE TO BRISBANE [GABBA]

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Back to 2020-21,

It was December, the ODI and T20I series was over, and it was time for the most awaited BORDER-GAVASKAR trophy (test series). We had won the previous one back in 2018 in Australia and were aiming to repeat it. Though, our team looked good, but the openers had less overseas experience. Virat could play only one match in the 4-match series due to family commitments, and Rohit couldn't come due to health issues. We had seen our tailenders bat with great courage in the practice match before. Our batting was at a toss, and it was going to be tough against ruthless bowlers like Starc, Cummins, and Hazlewood.

17th December 2020

ADELAIDE

It was 5:30 am in the morning, and I never woke up this early in my whole life, but, for watching this epic encounter, it was no big deal. The match started, and just on the second ball, Prithvi Shaw was bowled by Mitchell Starc. Not a good start. After this, all played steadily, and we were in a stable condition. Virat played a good knock of 70. With a decent 1st innings, we were 244 all out.

Aussies were up for batting and had a very strong batting lineup with David Warner, Steve Smith, Marcus Labuschagne... that was enough to state the danger. Tim Paine, their skipper, played a knock of 70, and they were all out for 191. Although they were 191 all out, giving us a very good chance to lead by a good score, what happened next was so unpredictable. We came to bat, the 1st wicket fell on 7, and then our batting lineup started collapsing, with a wicket almost after every 5 minutes. We were 36 all out, the lowest score in test cricket for India. Everyone thought our dreams of whitewashing/winning the series were shattered. These Aussies chased the target with ease, and the 1st match of the series was OVER.

BORDER GAVASKAR TROPHY 2020-2021: AUS 1-IND 0

Tweets all over the internet, press conferences, all criticized our players after the shameful defeat and that 36 all out, all scoring in single digits. Experts said/predicted about Aussies winning/whitewashing the series 4-0 straight. I too was very disappointed and had very little hope of India bouncing back into the series. Virat had departed from Australia. All were mocking our team in tweets, news, by cricket experts.

4 9 2 0 4 0 8 4 0 4 1- THIS IS NOT A PHONE NUMBER, BUT

These were the scores of our batting lineup. 36 ALL OUT!!!!

INDIA'S HORROR SHOW

LOWEST TEST TOTALS FOR THE TEAM

TOTAL	OPPOSITION	VENUE	YEAR
36	AUSTRALIA	ADELAIDE	2020
42	ENGLAND	LORD'S	1974
58	AUSTRALIA	BRISBANE	1947
58	ENGLAND	MANCHESTER	1952
66	SOUTH AFRICA	DURBAN	1996

India			2nd innings v Australia
P Shaw	b Cummins		4
M Agarwal	c Paine b Hazlewood		9
Jaspit Bumrah	c & b Cummins		2
C Pujara	c Paine b Cummins		0
V Kohli	c Green b Cummins		4
A Rahane	c Paine b Hazlewood		0
H Vihari	c Paine b Hazlewood		8
W Saha	c Labuschagne b Hazlewood		4
R Ashwin	c Paine b Hazlewood		0
U Yadav	not out		4
M Shami	ret hurt		1
Extras 0	Overs 21.2		36

1st test match:IND VS AUS[36 All OUT]

26th December 2020

MELBOURNE

Ajinkya Rahane's special knock in 2nd test

2nd Test at the MCG (Melbourne Cricket Ground). After that embarrassing loss, we were back. There were some changes in the team. We bowled them all out under the 200-run mark. They were all out for 195. Our innings started with a wicket in the very first over itself. After the wicket, it was stable, and the batsmen were playing under control. The main man here was AJINKYA RAHANE, the man who made 112 runs along with great support from Ravindra Jadeja -57. With their partnership, we reached a total of 326, and we were in a very good position. All bowlers bowled pretty well in the 2nd innings, which gave us a target of only 70. But, 70 too seemed risky as of what we saw in the 1st match. We chased it comfortably, and the series was 1: 1 in the 4-match series. That was our real start to the series. That was a good comeback, even though there were 2 matches to go...

BORDER GAVASKAR TROPHY 2020-2021: AUS 1-IND 1

7th January,2021

SYDNEY

Aussies to bat first. Though the 1st wicket fell on just 6 runs, their opener Willi Pucovski and Marcus Labuschagne had other plans. After building a good partnership, Willi Pucovski got out on 62 sending their best batsman STEVEN SMITH . They both, Labuschagne and Smith just went on to build a great partnership and scored 91 and 131 respectively. Thanks to the incredible run out by Ravindra Jadeja which got the dangerous Smith. They scored a total of 338. Then came our innings. We had no such big scoring batsman.

In that innings, all had hope on the man ,Rishabh Pant. We all remember the moment when, in 2018 he sledged Aussie captain in Australia, and gave them their own taste. He also had scored two 100's. You would be imagining why so much info about him. This would be getting covered very very, soon....We got all out on 244, having 50s from Shubhman Gill and Cheteshwar Pujara. The 3rd innings started and those batsmen, Labuschagne, and Smith, again started troubling us. They played with so much elegance scoring 73 and 81 respectively. They were out before 208, but then a Surprise package came in form of CAMERON GREEN who scored 84 and helped Aussies to get to a total of 312, which gave us a target of a mammoth 407 runs.

Our opening was good, but Gill got out on team's 71, and Rohit on team's 92. We had hope from our captain Rahane, but he too got out very early. Pujara, on the other hand, was playing really well. Then there came the man I mentioned earlier, Rishabh Pant, who is known for playing just ridiculous shots (one handed, hitting while losing balance,..) which end up going to a boundary, and that is the thing most of us, including me, like about him. He came and started playing in his own way. Along with Pujara scoring 77 runs, he played a knock of 97 runs, but all were very angry at him. He got out when we were in a very comfortable position, and he got out just recklessly.

Vihari and Ashwin were on the pitch. Vihari had a back injury, and Ashwin was also injured. Then too, they played for (42.4) overs, defending and not losing their wickets, as they were not in the condition to run. All were so proud of their determination. The next batsman, Jadeja, was also injured, having a thumb injury. Then too, he was ready to bat. This showed us determination and their love for the sport and country. When I started watching Vihari and

Ashwin, they were not running, though the ball was very far from any fielder. I was confused and frustrated at the same time, but when I heard of them being injured and still playing, I was just stunned. They played a whole session on that day. This was the moment of the match. The match was drawn, but this was much like a win. Just being too emotional at this moment.

Hanuma Vihari and Ravichandran Ashwin's special partnership

BORDER GAVASKAR TROPHY 2020-2021: AUS 1-IND 1

1 MATCH TO GO!!!

15th January,2021

BRISBANE

The series was now 1-1 with 1 match to go and on the unluckiest pitch to bowl on- Gabba. A flat pitch; a batsman's pitch. There were just 2 players in our team who played all the 4 matches, Ajinkya Rahane and Cheteshwar Pujara. There were so so many injuries in the team.

I still remember, in 2018 ,when we went to Australia for the series; Warner and Smith were banned due to ball tampering and their fans claiming that we won the series against a team

without their strong players. Now, this time, they had their strongest possible team as against inexperienced players in our team.

Here's a glimpse of our team for the final match :-

- Rohit, Gill-Very less experience (his 1st test series), Pujara, Rahane, Pant, Mayank- (not much experienced in the overseas)
- Sundar, Thakur, Saini - they would have played a total of 11-12 matches in international test cricket.
- Siraj, Natarajan-It was their debut series

To the Aussies saying those things back in 2018; this time we had no Virat, no Ashwin, no Jadeja, no Shami, no Bumrah, still what we did in the end was...

Not giving spoilers. Read it yourself..!!

So, the 4th test started, and their inform batsman, Marnus Labuschagne, scored a banger 108, and they had other cameos from Wade, Green, Paine, which got them to a total of 369. Our innings started well but did not go how we wished. We were 186 - 6, and our team was not in a safe condition.

Then came to bat, Washington Sundar and Shardul Thakur, who were having very little experience of international test cricket, but they were just so good on the pitch and had a splendid partnership of 123 runs. Thakur was so confident and started banging sixes, and scored a 50 as well with a 6. Sundar was playing very elegantly and both lifted up our team's confidence. Our innings ended on 336-10. Though we were trailing, it was not a very high difference.

Shardul Thakur and Washington Sundar's match changing partnership.

In their innings, our bowlers were just too good. Siraj got a five-wicket haul, and Thakur, a four-wicket haul. Sundar got the danger man, Warner. They were bowled all out for 294 runs. It was the 4th day of the match, we played just 1.5 overs, and there was the stumps. We had to make 324 runs on the last day in 90 overs, which was a huge target.

I remember the famous commentator Harsha Bhogle said that if we draw the match the next day, we should be happy, but if we win it, that would be one of the greatest wins in test cricket. It was so much suspenseful night for all the players, the fans.

The last day of this thriller match was going to start at 5:30 am. I was very much excited. I woke up after our Rohit was out. He was caught out on just team's 18 runs. After this Shubhman and Pujara started playing too good, controlled shots, elegant, and were heading towards a good partnership.

Shubhman Gill, the man who had a little experience in international cricket, was playing smooth and extraordinarily, that too against the Aussies (the fast-bowling unit, "Starc, Hazlewood, Cummins"). He made a score of 91 and helped us in that difficult chase.

Shubhman Gill's 91

After his good score, our captain came and played well right from the first ball, but got out on just 24 runs, Then, came the man (spiderman o spiderman...)-the fearless RISHABH PANT.....

Before talking about how Pant played on that day, there is a much-needed appreciation for the wall (not Sir Rahul Dravid), but Cheteshwar Pujara. He was hit at least 8-10 times by the Aussies; on helmet, arm, fingers, as well as on abdomen, still he did not give up. Here, I think we should thank the Aussies, for making a defensive man, an attacking man. He just

started smashing 4s and 6 s after getting hurt and made a very good partnership with Pant. He got out after a well-made 56.

We still needed 80 to win and now had just Pant, Shardul, Sundar. Mayank got out on 9 and was not effective in the series.

Now, nearly 60 to win, and..... be ready to have fun.

Pant, now was batting on a different level. How can he just hit those shots against those bowlers. He was sometimes hitting the scoop, sometimes reverse sweep, and the favourite of all, the one where he hit a six and fell. It was the most hilarious moment. He was just having fun and made around 80 runs.

Rishab Pant's unorthodox shots

We should also appreciate Sundar who played a very short but a very impactful innings after which, the target now was very very easy to chase... but... He played just a very very ridiculous reverse sweep, which was not at all needed at that time and got out. Just 10-15 runs were needed

We shouldn't get angry before seeing the greatest moment ever. Coming back, Shardul also got out just in 3 balls...

Let's get back to Pant. He has played an extraordinary innings of 85 till now. Saini came to bat. Now 3 runs needed to win (sufficient balls to go). Pant on strike, he drives it, and they take a run, goes for the second, and that's a 4, they win.... They have done it and whole stadium is cheering. Navdeep Saini also had back pain, I heard in an interview of Pant, that he made Saini run so fast, that he just forgot about the pain, but what happened next was way more than that little pain.

BORDER GAVASKAR TROPHY 2020-2021: AUS 1-IND 2 [WE HAVE WON IT]

Whenever I think of this match, there is just 1 line which comes to my mind:-

टूटा है गाबा का घमंड, जीत गई है भारत ये मुकाबला

GABBA HAS BEEN CONQUERED, AND WE HAVE WON THE SERIES BY 2-1

The special winning moment

There are many moments, things which motivates everyone, when they are in pain, or depression. This series is that medicine for me. It just gives me goosebumps every time I watch it and make me believe, that its never the end. Just keep moving.

After 36 All Out, every single player of our team was humiliated, made fun of, everyone just started bashing our team.

At this time there were 2 main people:- Ravi Shastri and Ajinkya Rahane. They both just changed the mindset of our team.

Ajinkya Rahane would also be appreciated for backing his players like Siraj who faced racist remarks by the Aussies crowd.

Our mindset changed after this series:

If they hit bouncers to our tailenders, either they would be smashed for boundaries, or would be taken care of in the 2nd innings (with our bowling).

The series winning moment. The stars of the final game at the Gabba